

Research paper

HalalChain: A decentralized blockchain model for enhanced data integrity, real-time compliance, and automated verification in halal food supply chain

Muhammad Muntasir Yakubu^{a,b,*}, Mohd Fadzil B Hassan^a, Kamaluddeen Usman Danyaro^a, Bello Musa Yakubu^c, Abdullah Abdulrahman Alabdulatif^d, S. Zulaikha Beevi^e, Aliyu Garba^a

^a Department of Computing, Faculty of Science, Management and Computing, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Perak 32610, Malaysia

^b Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Computing, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina 5001, Nigeria

^c Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Faculty of Science, Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

^d Department of Cybersecurity, College of Computer, Qassim University, Buraydah 52571, Saudi Arabia

^e Department of Computer Science and Engineering JCT College of Engineering and Technology Coimbatore, 641105 Tamil Nadu, India

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ABSTRACT

The global halal food industry, valued at over \$1.9 trillion, faces critical challenges in ensuring transparency, traceability, and compliance with Islamic dietary laws across complex supply chains. Traditional centralized systems are vulnerable to inefficiencies, fraud, and data tampering, undermining consumer trust. This paper introduces HalalChain, a blockchain-based model designed to address these gaps through decentralized verification, automated compliance, and tamper-proof data integrity. HalalChain integrates Proof of Authority (PoA) consensus, cryptographic hashing, Merkle Trees, and IoT sensors to enforce halal-specific protocols, such as ritual slaughter validation (Bismillah Allahu Akbar invocation) and cross-contamination monitoring. Key innovations include threshold cryptography for decentralized authority consensus, smart contracts for real-time Islamic compliance checks, and privacy-preserving decentralized identifiers (DIDs). Experimental evaluations demonstrate HalalChain's superiority over existing models (AgriFoodCredChain, AgriBlockIoT), achieving a 99.8 % tamper detection rate, transaction throughput (38 TPS), consensus times of 1.2–2.5 s, 98 % validator approval rate, and optimal compliance adherence under varying loads. The framework reduces reliance on intermediaries, automates halal certification, and enhances operational efficiency while safeguarding sensitive data. These advancements position HalalChain as a transformative solution for strengthening trust, regulatory enforcement, and ethical integrity in halal supply chains globally.

1. Introduction

The global halal food industry is rapidly growing, valued at over \$1.9 trillion in 2023, with increasing demand from Muslim consumers and those seeking ethical products [1,2]. Despite this growth, ensuring transparency, traceability, and compliance with halal standards across complex supply chains remains a challenge. Halal certification requires compliance with Islamic law, including ritual slaughter by certified personnel invoking "Bismillah Allahu Akbar" (*In the name of Allah; Allah is the Greatest*) (Quran 6:118 and Hadith Sahih Muslim); bans on haram substances (e.g., pork derivatives, alcohol); and segregation from non-halal products during storage or transport [3,4]. The existing

blockchain models prioritize generic traceability but lack automated ritual checks or decentralized halal certification [5,6]. Regulatory inconsistencies exacerbate these issues. Halal certification standards vary significantly across regions, complicating cross-border trade and enforcement. The lack of transparency further undermines consumer and regulator confidence in certified products [1]. Blockchain technology offers a transformative solution by providing a decentralized, tamper-proof platform for recording and verifying transactions [7]. In halal supply chains, blockchain ensures secure documentation of every step, from sourcing to certification. Smart contracts automate compliance checks, streamlining regulatory processes and reducing delays [8]. Privacy-preserving features, such as decentralized identifiers (DIDs),

* Corresponding author at: Department of Computing, Faculty of Science, Management and Computing, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Perak 32610, Malaysia.
E-mail address: muhammad_22010099@utp.edu.my (M.M. Yakubu).

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safeguard sensitive data while maintaining traceability [9].

This article makes several pivotal contributions to the field of halal food supply chain management and security, leveraging the power of blockchain technology. An enhanced presentation of these contributions is provided below:

- **Decentralized Halal Compliance Verification:** Leveraging Proof of Authority (PoA) consensus and threshold cryptography to decentralize certification approvals among pre-approved halal authorities, eliminating single points of failure and insider fraud.
- **Halal – Centric IoT and Smart Contracts:** Integrating IoT devices to monitor cross-contamination risks (e.g., shared storage temperatures) and automate compliance with Islamic protocols (e.g., *Bismillah Allahu Akbar* invocation, slaughter credentials) via smart contracts.
- **Privacy-Preserving Halal Integrity:** Ensuring data authenticity via cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees, while maintaining stakeholder anonymity through DIDs.
- **Halal-Optimized Performance:** Demonstrating superior tamper detection, compliance adherence, and transaction throughput compared to models like AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT.

Through these contributions, our study not only addresses critical gaps in current halal food supply chain management practices but also lays the groundwork for future advancements in the secure and effective use of blockchain technology in halal certification and beyond.

The paper is structured to provide a comprehensive view of the model. It begins with an introduction to challenges in halal food supply chains, followed by a literature review highlighting gaps in existing solutions. The methodology elaborates on the model's architecture, including IoT integration and decentralized verification mechanisms. Experimental evaluations demonstrate HalalChain's superior performance in data integrity and compliance adherence. The discussion contextualizes its advancements compared to other models, and the conclusion emphasizes its transformative potential for the halal food industry. Limitations including scalability challenges, high operational costs, and potential network congestion are acknowledged; future enhancements such as optimized consensus mechanisms, cost-effective blockchain platforms, and privacy-preserving techniques are proposed to support wider adoption, regulatory alignment, and long-term sustainability.

2. Literature review

Blockchain technology is transforming agrifood and halal food supply chains by enhancing transparency, traceability, and data integrity [10]. Originally designed for cryptocurrencies, blockchain now addresses key challenges like food safety and fraud, providing a decentralized, tamper-proof platform for secure transaction recording [10–14]. Its relevance in the halal food sector is particularly significant due to strict compliance with Islamic dietary laws and the need for trustworthy certification processes [15]. Jurisprudential (*fiqh*) and regulatory fragmentation creates significant halal compliance complexity across regions, authorities, and key requirements like slaughter methods, substance prohibitions, with cross-contamination and governance [16].

Studies reveal blockchain adoption in halal supply chains improves performance, builds consumer trust, and boosts competitiveness, as evidenced by research on Indonesian firms and Malaysian frameworks for small and medium enterprises [9,17–24]. These frameworks stress the importance of regulatory support and integration to overcome adoption barriers, such as technological and financial constraints. Recent advancements in blockchain databases, such as LedgerDB, VeDB, and SecuDB, focus on high performance and tamper resistance, offering centralized solutions with enhanced auditability, real-time verification, and privacy features [9,25]. However, these systems are centralized,

raising concerns about trust, insider threats, and vulnerability to manipulation. In contrast, HalalChain proposes a decentralized verification approach using blockchain technology to ensure data integrity and eliminate single points of failure. By leveraging decentralized consensus and threshold cryptography, HalalChain enhances security, transparency, and accountability in halal certification, minimizing risks associated with insider fraud and tampering, thus providing a scalable, tamper-proof solution for halal food supply chains.

While previous blockchain-based traceability systems such as AgriFoodCredChain [5], AgriBlockIoT [6], and AgriOnBlock [26], have explored decentralized trust and IoT integration, they lack specialized mechanisms for real-time halal ritual compliance, multi-party certification, and jurisprudential adaptability. AgriFoodCredChain emphasizes basic traceability but relies on semi-centralized verification, whereas AgriBlockIoT lacks formal consensus security proofs and tamper detection mechanisms tailored to religious contexts. HalalChain advances the field by introducing threshold cryptography, dynamic smart contracts adaptable to different halal authorities, and ProVerif-verified consensus logic to counter Sybil and Byzantine attacks. This approach uniquely fuses Islamic regulatory requirements with blockchain formalism bridging the trust, compliance, and security gaps in prior models. Additional insights were drawn from broader cross-disciplinary literature in blockchain security, Islamic finance, and IoT-driven governance models.

Notably, no existing system fully automates checks like the 'Bismillah' invocation or uses threshold cryptography for certifier consensus [6, 27–29]. While recent advances—including decentralized identifiers (DIDs), verifiable credentials (VCs), and smart contracts—are promising for automated and secure halal certification, challenges remain around scalability, costs, and regulatory alignment [27–29]. To fully realize blockchain's benefits for halal supply chains, it is vital to enhance cryptographic methods and develop consistent standards, which would further boost transparency, efficiency, and consumer trust.

Table 1 summarizes the key studies related to blockchain applications in supply chain management, highlighting their objectives, focus areas, and limitations. The proposed HalalChain model addresses these gaps by offering a comprehensive solution that integrates decentralized verification, IoT monitoring, and smart contracts to ensure transparency, traceability, and compliance in halal food supply chains.

2.1. Problem statement and objectives of the study

Studies have investigated halal food supply chain faces significant challenges in upholding compliance with Islamic jurisprudence, compounded by critical vulnerabilities in existing blockchain-based certification systems. While blockchain technology offers decentralized traceability, current implementations remain inadequate in addressing halal-specific risks, which erode trust and regulatory efficiency. The systems reveal two major challenges: centralized data verification and data integrity vulnerabilities. Existing systems in halal food supply chains often rely on centralized initial verification processes, which undermine blockchain's decentralization, create single points of failure, and expose the system to insider threats (single corrupt certifier) [6,9,19,38]. This issue is exacerbated by the absence of mechanisms to prevent unilateral authority, as highlighted in studies on centralized blockchain frameworks [9,18,38]. Furthermore, existing systems lack automated checks for Islamic protocols, such as mandatory invocation or humane slaughter methods, creating risks of ritual non-compliance that invalidate halal status [14,39]. Compounding these challenges is the risk of cross-contamination, as generic IoT devices fail to enforce halal-specific rules for segregating products during storage and transportation, leading to potential breaches of purity standards [3,40]. These gaps, coupled with weak authentication protocols, inadequate security measure, and vulnerabilities to data tampering or man-in-the-middle attacks [41–43], expose the supply chain to systemic failures and diminish stakeholder confidence.

Table 1
Summary of related works.

References	Objectives	Focus areas	Limitations	Halal – specific gaps
[12,30–32]	Blockchain integration for traceability	Transparency, traceability, and efficiency in supply chains	Lacks robust scalability solutions; limited focus on end-user control	No ritual compliance checks (Bismillah invocation, slaughterer validation); generic IoT rules, not halal-optimized
[33,34]	Data access mechanisms for accountability	Stakeholder accountability and access control	Incomplete end-user controls; increased system complexity	Centralized validation; no threshold cryptography for halal authority consensus
[15]	Improving halal certification processes	Real-time tracking and certification validation	Limited consumer usability and flexibility	Manual compliance checks; lacks automated smart contracts for Islamic protocols
[17,23]	Enhancing interoperability in blockchain	Regional regulatory compliance and system interoperability	Challenges in aligning with diverse regulatory environments	No cross-contamination monitoring or halal-centric IoT integration
[35,36]	Privacy-centric blockchain models	User-centric operations and privacy preservation	Limited scalability and high deployment costs for smaller markets	Anonymity for halal certifiers not ensured via DIDs
[37]	Decentralized frameworks for auditing	Real-time auditing and transparency in agrifood supply chains	Scalability and regulatory alignment remain unresolved	No decentralized halal authority consensus; lacks ritual compliance audits
HalalChain (This Study)	Halal – specific blockchain traceability	Decentralized verification, IoT integration, privacy-preserving compliance	Scalability under extreme loads	Addresses all gaps above: ritual compliance, halal-centric IoT, threshold cryptography for authorities, DID-based anonymity

To address these shortcomings, this study introduces HalalChain, a blockchain-based model designed to redefine halal compliance through tailored innovations. The first objective is to eliminate centralized vulnerabilities by implementing threshold cryptography, which decentralizes authority and requires consensus from multiple pre-approved halal certifiers, thereby mitigating insider fraud. Second, the model integrates smart contracts to automate ritual compliance, ensuring adherence to Islamic protocols such as validating slaughterer credentials and Bismillah invocations at every supply chain node. Third, HalalChain incorporates halal-centric IoT sensors to monitor critical parameters like temperature thresholds and hygiene status, enforcing real-time segregation of halal and non-halal products to prevent cross-contamination. Finally, the model leverages cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees to establish end-to-end data integrity, safeguarding certification records against tampering during data entry. By addressing these objectives, HalalChain aims to create a resilient, universally

trusted model that upholds Islamic dietary laws, strengthens consumer confidence, and streamlines regulatory oversight in halal supply chains.

3. Preliminaries

This section covers the foundational aspects of the overall system model, including the network model, attacker model, system requirement, and comprehensively explain the model’s workflow structure.

3.1. Network model

The HalalChain network model ensures data integrity, transparency, and decentralized verification in the halal food supply chain by combining blockchain, IoT devices, and decentralized authorities. This section details the network architecture, key components, and includes a structural diagram, as illustrated in Fig. 1 below. Traditional high-

Fig. 1. Network model.

performance databases like LedgerDB, VeDB, and SecuDB offer auditability and privacy but rely on centralized trust, which does not align with the multi-stakeholder nature of halal certification [9,25]. In contrast, HalalChain's blockchain-based architecture, using consensus and threshold cryptography, offers a more robust and decentralized solution for data integrity and automated compliance.

For practical deployment, integrating lightweight decentralized databases, our study proposed model employs the Ethereum blockchain (ET_{Bc}) as the base infrastructure for HalalChain offers a promising path to balance performance, trust distribution, and religious compliance. This is to ensure data integrity (I_d) and facilitate decentralized verification (V_d) across the halal food supply chain. The network architecture consists of three primary components: IoT devices (D_{IoT}), blockchain nodes (N_{Bc}), and decentralized authorities (A_d), working collaboratively to safeguard the integrity of halal food certification and processes, as illustrated in Fig. 1. All the mathematical symbols and equations follow standardized cryptographic and blockchain notation [44–48].

IoT devices ($dev \in D_{IoT}$) authenticate and transmit data to the blockchain through a hybrid approach combining on-chain smart contracts and off-chain verification. Each device cryptographically signs raw data (D_i) using its private key (PrK_{E_i}), ensuring authenticity via $D_{IoT} = \text{Sign}_{PrK_{E_i}}(hf((D_i)))$, where hf represents the SHA-256 hash function. Before blockchain submission, edge preprocessing filters and validates data using halal-specific compliance rules, such as enforcing temperature thresholds (e.g., $0^\circ\text{C} \leq t \leq 4^\circ\text{C}$ for fresh meat) and hygiene standards, flagging non-compliant entries (e.g., out-of-range temperatures). Validated data is hashed ($hf(D_i)$) and directly written to the ET_{Bc} via smart contracts, bypassing third-party oracles to reduce latency and trust risks. These hashes are then aggregated into a Merkle Tree: leaf nodes ($L_i = hf(D_i)$) are iteratively concatenated and hashed to form parent nodes ($P_{i,j} = hf(L_i || L_j)$), culminating in a tamper-proof Merkle Root (R) stored on-chain. This root enables efficient verification of data integrity across the supply chain, ensuring transparency and compliance with Islamic protocols.

For data collection and hashing, each $dev \in D_{IoT}$ collects real-time data D_i , such as food source (fs), processing details (pd), transportation logs (tl), temperature (t) and location (l), throughout the supply chain. The raw data D_i is hashed using the SHA-256 cryptographic hash function $hf()$. These hashes are aggregated into leaf nodes L_i in a Merkle Tree, where $L_i = hf(D_i)$. Then the adjacent leaf nodes are concatenated and hashed iteratively, forming parent nodes $P_{i,j} = hf(L_i || L_j)$, until the root hash R is generated. The Merkle root R provides a compact representation of the dataset and ensures safe data verification.

Therefore, in the blockchain storage and verification, the hashed data D_i and $L_i = hf(D_i)$ are transmitted to the Ethereum blockchain (ET_{Bc}), where they are stored in a tamper-resistant manner. By leveraging SHA-256 hashing, any modification to the original data D_i results in a drastically different hash $hf(D_i) \neq hf(D'_i)$. The immutability of the blockchain ensures that all recorded transactions are secure and traceable, safeguarding the integrity of the data. Smart contracts on the Ethereum blockchain automate data verification, ensuring compliance with halal standards and initiating actions upon validation of the data. For instance, if D_i represents a transportation log (tl), the smart contract checks compliance $C(D_i)$ where $C(D_i) \rightarrow \text{valid}$ if all criteria are met. These results are stored on the blockchain, providing transparency and accountability in the supply chain. Smart contracts trigger predefined actions, such as rejecting non-compliant data or flagging anomalies, ensuring adherence to halal standards.

To validate transactions (Tx), the system utilizes a PoA consensus mechanism, it offers fast, secure consensus with trusted validators, low latency, Sybil resistance, and efficient performance for halal certification systems [49,50]. It is defined by: $C_{PoA} = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$. Where V_i represents validators such as halal certifiers and regulatory authorities.

Validators verify the accuracy of transactions,

$$(Tx) : \forall Tx \in ET_{Bc}, V_i(Tx) \xrightarrow{\text{auth}} \text{Approval} \quad (1)$$

Hence, for security critical decisions (D_c) require threshold cryptographic consensus: $T_c = [2n/3]$, where T_c defines the minimum number of validators needed to approve D_c . For example, with $n = 5$ halal authorities, at least T_c approvals are required, mitigating insider threats and ensuring secure, decentralized verification. This mechanism prevents unilateral control over critical processes, such as entity registration or certification validation.

The combination of blockchain immutability, PoA consensus, and threshold cryptography provides a transparent, tamper-resistant system. The resilience of the model (R_x) against manipulation can be expressed as:

$$R_x = f(ET_{Bc}, SC, T_c, C_{PoA}) \quad (2)$$

Where f denotes the functional collaboration of blockchain, smart contracts (SC), threshold cryptography, and PoA consensus. This model guarantees a robust, secure, and decentralized framework, ensuring confidence in the halal certification process and the overall integrity of the supply chain.

The following are brief descriptions of the model guide in each stage.

- **Initial Data Input:** Suppliers submit ingredients and slaughter data.
- **Decentralized Verification:** Threshold cryptography ensures multiple entities verify data.
- **Data Integrity:** Cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees ensure tamper-proof records.
- **IoT Monitoring:** Sensors track real-time storage and transportation conditions.
- **Slaughter Compliance:** Smart contracts enforce halal standards for slaughtering.
- **Final Certification:** All verified data is recorded on the blockchain for full traceability.

3.2. Adversarial model

The HalalChain model ensures data integrity, transparency, and decentralized verification in the halal food supply chain. However, it is susceptible to various adversarial attacks. This section outlines potential attack vectors and assumptions about the adversary's capabilities.

1) Data Tampering

An adversary may alter data from IoT devices or stored on the blockchain, such as temperature logs, forging slaughter timestamps or ingredient details. The tampered data could lead to non-compliant products being certified as halal, undermining trust and compliance. But cryptographic hashing (e.g., SHA-256) and Merkle Trees can detect any data alterations.

2) Insider Attacks

A corrupt halal certifier may abuse privileges to approve non-compliant products (e.g., certifying meat lacking Bismillah invocation), leading to fraudulent halal certifications. In this, threshold cryptography, which requires multiple approvals, will reduce the risk of these threats. While smart contracts are enforced programmatically, reducing human intervention.

3) Blockchain Node Compromise

An adversary may compromise blockchain nodes to alter transaction records or disrupt the network. Compromising the nodes could validate fraudulent transactions or reject legitimate ones, undermining reliability. Therefore, the PoA consensus ensures only approved validators participate, and blockchain immutability makes past records difficult to alter.

4. Proposed HalalChain model

The HalalChain model uses Ethereum (Sepolia public testnet) blockchain technology, cryptographic methods, and decentralized systems to guarantee data integrity and prevent manipulation in halal food supply chains, while simultaneously tackling the problem of centralized initial verification. The full list of symbols is provided in Appendix A, with a comprehensive overview of all symbols used in the study along with their respective definitions (see Table A in glossary of symbols of appendix A). The proposed model is achieved via two main first stages: Registration Stage for Verification of Entities and Halal Certification Records; second stage: Supply Chain Data Integrity and Decentralized Verification Stage.

4.1. Registration stage for entities and halal certification records

The registration process ensures the inclusion of trusted entities, such as certification bodies or halal authorities, into the blockchain system. This stage comprises three main phases: Initial Registration Bootstrap, Decentralized Registration for Subsequent Entities, and Halal Certification Record Registration, as illustrated in Fig. 2 below. A smart contract written in Solidity enforces decentralized registration rules. For example, *SC.Registration.sol* verifies validator signatures and requires T_c approval before recording entities on-chain. Code snippets are provided in supplementary files.

Phase 1: Initial Registration Bootstrap

When the system was first established, there were no existing entities to provide decentralized approval. To address this, a Genesis Group (G_0) is formed to bootstrap the system.

- Governing Authority or Trusted Entities Setup:** A central governing authority or a pre-agreed set of reputable organizations (the Genesis Group) is manually identified and verified. These entities are well-established in halal certification and known for their integrity.
- Manual Registration of Initial Entities:** Each entity in the Genesis Group is registered with its unique identifier (ID_{E_i}), public key (PK_{E_i}), and

additional metadata such as certification scope or region (M_{E_i}). The blockchain records the registration as follows:

$$R_{E_i} = hf(ID_{E_i} || PK_{E_i} || M_{E_i} || T_{E_i}) \quad (3)$$

Where T_{E_i} is the timestamp of registration.

- Smart Contract Initialization:** A smart contract is deployed to enforce the rules for decentralized registration, ensuring transparency and security in all future approvals.
- Threshold Cryptography Parameters Setup:** The system initializes a threshold T_c for decentralized approvals and defines the total number of initial entities E_n in the Genesis Group.

However, in cases where no entities exist in the system at the initial stage, a temporary central trusted authority ($Admin_{temp}$) manually registers the first set of entities (Genesis Group). Once the Genesis Group is established, the system enforces decentralized registration through the smart contract.

Phase 2: Decentralized Registration for Subsequent Entities

Once the Genesis Group is established, the system transitions to decentralized registration, leveraging threshold cryptography to prevent centralized control.

1. Entity Registration Request: New entities (E_{n+1}) submit their request for registration, providing:

- Unique identifier ($ID_{E_{n+1}}$)
- Public key ($PK_{E_{n+1}}$)
- Certification scope/metadata ($M_{E_{n+1}}$)

2. Decentralized Approval via Threshold Cryptography: The registration request is submitted to all currently authorized entities for verification. Each entity E_i evaluates the request and provides an approval (a_i) or rejection:

Fig. 2. Workflow diagram for the proposed model.

$$a_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } E_i \text{ approves the registration,} \\ 0 & \text{if } E_i \text{ rejects the registration.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

For registration to be valid, the sum of approval must meet or exceed the threshold T_c :

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \geq T_c \quad (5)$$

3. Blockchain Record Creation: Upon successful verification, the new entity's details are recorded on the blockchain:

$$R_{E_{n+1}} = hf(ID_{E_{n+1}} \parallel PK_{E_{n+1}} \parallel M_{E_{n+1}} \parallel T_{E_{n+1}}) \quad (6)$$

Phase3: Halal Certification Record Registration

Simultaneously, halal certification records are also registered and linked to the respective entities:

1. Certification Details: Each halal certification (C_j) includes:

- Certification ID (ID_{C_j})
- Certified products or services (P_{C_j})
- Issuer entity ID (ID_{E_i})
- Validity period (V_{C_j})
- Certification timestamp (T_{C_j})

2. Blockchain Storage: Certification records are hashed and stored on the blockchain, enabling quick and secure verification:

$$R_{C_j} = hf(ID_{C_j} \parallel P_{C_j} \parallel ID_{E_i} \parallel V_{C_j} \parallel T_{C_j}) \quad (7)$$

3. Linking Entities and Certifications: Certifications are linked to their issuing entities for seamless validation during the verification process.

The [algorithm 1](#)'s registration process has $O(n)$ time complexity, where n is the number of validators. Each entity registration involves hashing ($O(1)$), n validator approvals ($O(n)$), and blockchain storage ($O(1)$)."

4.2. Supply chain data integrity and decentralized verification stage

This stage consists of five phases: initial data input, data integrity verification, supply chain tracking, slaughtering compliance, and final product certification.

Algorithm 1

Registration stage for entities and halal certification records.

Input: $D_i : \{ID, SD, IoT\}, T_c, PID$.

Output: V_{result} (registration status).

Procedure:

Phase 1: Initial Registration Bootstrap

- From Genesis Group: $G_0 = \{ID_{E_i}, PK_{E_i}, M_{E_i}\}$

- Record Initial Entities:

$$R_{E_i} \leftarrow hf(ID_{E_i}, PK_{E_i}, M_{E_i}, T_{E_i})$$

- Set Threshold Parameters: $T_c \leq E_n$

- Deploy Smart Contracts:

$$SC_{init} : \forall R_i \text{ if } V_i \geq T_c \Rightarrow R_i \in N_{Bc}$$

Phase 2: Decentralized Registration for Subsequent Entities

- Submit Registration Request: $R_i : \{ID_{E_i}, PK_{E_i}, M_{E_i}\}$

- Decentralized Approval:

$$\sum_{v \in V} a_{v,i} a_{v,i} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } v \text{ approves } R_i \\ 0, & \text{if } v \text{ rejects } R_i \end{cases}$$

$$R_i \text{ is approved if } V_i \geq T_c$$

- Store on Blockchain: $N_{Bc} \leftarrow \{ID_{E_i}, PK_{E_i}, M_{E_i}, prev_{hash}\}$ if $V_i \geq T_c$

Phase 3: Halal Certification Record Registration

- Submit Certification Details: $C_i = \{CertID_i, P_i, ID_{E_i}, V_i, prev_{hash}\}$

- Hash and Link Certification Data: $hf(C_i) = hf(\{CertID_i, P_i, ID_{E_i}, V_i, prev_{hash}\})$

- Store Certification on Blockchain: $N_{Bc} \leftarrow \{hf(C_i), ID_{E_i}, CertID_i, prev_{hash}\}$

- Enable Verification:

$$V_{cert}(CertID_i) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } N_{Bc} \ni \{hf(C_i), ID_{E_i}, CertID_i\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

End Procedure

As illustrated in [Fig. 2](#). In the initial data input phase, suppliers provide data, such as ingredient details, which are validated against certification records using smart contracts. Data integrity is ensured by organizing hashed data into a Merkle Tree, where the Merkle Root detects tampering. Supply chain tracking utilizes IoT devices to monitor real-time conditions like temperature and hygiene, ensuring compliance with halal standards. The slaughtering compliance phase records details of the slaughtering process and validates adherence to Islamic protocols using smart contracts. Finally, the certification phase links products to their supply chain data using unique identifiers stored on the blockchain, enabling transparent verification by consumers and auditors.

Phase 1: Initial data input and certification verification

1. Data input: In this phase, trusted suppliers or slaughterhouses input critical data into the system. This data includes Ingredients Details (ID): $ID = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n\}$. Where each i_j denotes an ingredient with its halal certification. Slaughter Details (SD): $SD = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m\}$ Where each s_{id} contains essential information such as the slaughterer's ID, method of slaughter, and timestamp of the process. IoT devices (D_{IoT}) are deployed at various points in the supply chain to gather real-time data, such as temperature t , location l etc, ensuring precise tracking and compliance monitoring.

2. Verification via Smart Contract: Each data input submitted is subjected to an automated verification process using a smart contract. The smart contract cross-references the input data with stored halal certification records. This ensures that the data corresponds to valid, pre-registered certifications. The verification process is mathematically expressed as:

$$V_{cert(x)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } hf(x) = R_{C_j} \text{ (valid certification)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Where: $hf(x)$ is the cryptographic hash of the input data.

R_{C_j} is the stored hash of the valid certification. HalalChain encodes core halal rules in smart contracts, enabling configurable logic by authorities to manage jurisprudential differences and ambiguity.

3. Decentralized Verification with Threshold Cryptography: To prevent reliance on a single entity and mitigate risks of centralized control, the system employs threshold cryptography for decentralized verification. The following parameters are considered:

Authorized Entities (E): A set of validators including certification bodies and regulatory authorities: $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n\}$.

Threshold Cryptography (T_c): The minimum number of approvals needed verification, e.g., $T_c \leq n$, e.g. $T_c = 3$ out of $n = 5$.

Approval mechanism: Each entity can give an endorsement or a denial about a product's legitimacy. Verification is deemed valid if a minimum of T_c entities provide approval.

Approval set: given that a set of n entities $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_n\}$, each entity E_i will provide an approval a_i , such that:

$$a_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } E_i \text{ approves the product} \\ 0, & \text{if } E_i \text{ rejects the product} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Verification condition: For verification to succeed, the aggregate of approvals must meet or exceed the threshold T_c :

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i \geq T_c \quad (10)$$

Leveraging the blockchain's immutability and decentralized verification mechanism, the system ensures a tamper-resistant and transparent framework. Threshold cryptography enhances confidence in the certification process by distributing trust among multiple validators, thereby safeguarding the halal supply chain against fraud and manipulation.

Phase 2: Data Integrity Using Cryptographic Hashing and Merkle Trees

The second phase ensures data integrity by leveraging cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees. This phase focuses on securing data collected from IoT devices and providing tamper-proof verification through the

blockchain.

- Data Collection and Hashing:** each IoT device ($dev_i \in D_{IoT}$) installed across the halal food supply chain collects real-time data (D_i), and the raw data is hashed using the SHA-256 cryptographic function $L_i = hf(D_i)$, where L_i represents the hash of the collected data, serving as a leaf node in the Merkle Tree.
- Merkle Tree Construction:** The Merkle Tree aggregates hashed data into a hierarchical structure for efficient verification. Each $L_i = hf(D_i)$, becomes a leaf node, and adjacent leaf nodes are concatenated and hashed iteratively: $P_{i,j} = hf(L_i || L_j)$ where $||$ denotes concatenation. Then the process continues until a single root hash (R), the Merkle Root, is computed $R = hf(P_{1,2} || P_{3,4})$. Until the Merkle Root provides a compact representation of the entire dataset and ensures safe verification.
- Blockchain Storage and Verification:** The hashed data ($L_i = hf(D_i)$) and the Merkle Root (R) are stored immutably on the Ethereum blockchain (ET_{Bc}). The blockchain ensures that any modification to the original data (D_i) results in a drastically different hash $hf(D_i) \neq hf(D'_i)$ safeguarding the integrity of stored data. Smart contracts on ET_{Bc} automate data verification to ensure compliance, $C(D_i) \rightarrow valid$ if all criteria are met. Non-compliant data is flagged, rejected, or triggers predefined actions.
- Tamper Detection with Merkle Proofs:** The Merkle Root enables efficient verification: A verifier retrieves the transaction hash (L_x) and its sibling hashes. The Merkle Path is reconstructed iteratively: $R' = hf(L_x || L_s)$ where L_s represents sibling hashes along the path. The reconstructed root (R') is compared to the stored Merkle Root

$$(R) : R' = R \Rightarrow Valid Transaction \quad (11)$$

By integrating cryptographic hashing, Merkle Trees, and blockchain immutability, this phase ensures that all data in the halal food supply chain is verifiable, tamper-proof, and secure. The use of smart contracts further enhances transparency and accountability by automating compliance checks. This combination guarantees the integrity of data and instills trust in the halal certification process.

Phase 3: Supply Chain Tracking with IoT Sensors and Tamper Detection

1. Real-Time Data Collection: IoT devices (D_{IoT}) are strategically deployed across the halal food supply chain at farms, processing facilities, transportation hubs, and storage units. These devices collect real-time data (D_i), including Temperature (t), Hygiene status (δ), Transportation logs (tl), Processing details (pd), Location (l). Each collected data point is hashed using the SHA-256 cryptographic function

$$hf(x) = SHA.256(t || \delta_i || tl || pd || l || T_{E_i}) \quad (12)$$

2. Permissible Parameter Ranges: The model incorporates predefined thresholds for temperature and hygiene values to ensure food safety and compliance with halal standards. Temperature thresholds for halal meat storage (Table 2) and hygiene status criteria (Table 3) ensure compliance with Islamic standards, as mandated by the Islamic Food and Nutrition Council of America (IFANCA) [51,52].

For hygiene, environmental and procedural cleanliness is categorized as:

3. Tamper-Detection Mechanisms: Four mechanisms are employed in this model to ensure the identification of any anomalies in sensor data before storage:

Digital Signatures for Sensor Data: First, each IoT sensor signs the data collected with its private key (PrK_{E_i}) to ensure authenticity as follows:

$$D_{IoT} = Sign_{PrK_{E_i}}(hf_{IoT}) \quad (13)$$

Anomaly Detection with Threshold Checks: We define acceptable ranges for temperature and hygiene values. An anomaly is detected if the

sensor data falls outside these ranges:

- Temperature threshold: $t_{min} \leq t_i \leq t_{max}$
- Hygiene status: $\delta_i = "clean"$
- The anomaly detection function can be given as:

$$A_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (t_i \notin [t_{min}, t_{max}]) \text{ or } (\delta_i \neq \text{clean}) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $A_i = 1$ indicates an anomaly.

Periodic Integrity Checks: The sensors devices are configured to periodically send integrity checksums to verify that they have not been compromised.

Immutable Logs: All sensor data and tamper-detection results are immutably stored on the blockchain for auditing.

The hashed data $hf()$ is transmitted to the blockchain, where smart contracts automatically validate compliance: $C(D_i) \rightarrow valid$ if criteria are met. Non-compliant data triggers predefined actions, such as rejecting the data or flagging anomalies for further investigation.

Phase 4: Slaughtering Compliance

This phase ensure that all Islamic slaughtering protocol is fully observed, complied and recorded as according to Islamic jurisprudence.

1. Slaughter Record Input: Each slaughter record (SR) includes: S_{id} A unique identifier for the slaughterer. Religious invocation, ensuring "Bismillah" is pronounced. The exact time t the slaughtering process is performed. After collecting the data, the system will now compute its hash as follows:

$$hf_{SR} = SHA.256(S_{id} || B || t) \quad (15)$$

2. Blockchain Storage: The hashed slaughter record (hf_{SR}) is transmitted to the Ethereum blockchain (ET_{Bc}) for immutable storage. Any tampering with the record (SR) would result in a mismatch between the computed and stored hash:

$$hf_{SR} \neq hf'_{SR} \Rightarrow Data Tampering Detected \quad (16)$$

3. Smart Contract Validation: The system employs a smart contract (SC) to verify compliance with Islamic slaughtering standards. The validation process ensures: The invocation (B) matches the required standard ("Bismillah"). The slaughterer ID (S_{id}) is verified against a list of authorized personnel. For example, during slaughter, the IoT device records the slaughterer's ID and whether the "Bismillah" invocation is recited. The smart contract checks against on-chain certification records. If either is missing or unauthorized, the contract flags and rejects the batch automatically. This real-time process enforces halal compliance without manual intervention.

$$C_{slaughter} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } B = "Bismillah" \text{ and } S_{id} \text{ is valid} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

The smart contract verifies the slaughterer's authorization and the presence of the Bismillah invocation before certifying a batch. The compliance checking process is illustrated in Fig. 3 below.

The flowchart above outlines the decision-making steps taken by the smart contract during the slaughtering stage. To further clarify the automation process, the following pseudocode provides a simplified representation of how HalalChain's smart contract verifies compliance

Table 2

Temperature ranges for halal food items.

Food Type	Acceptable temperature range
Fresh Meat (e.g., beef, poultry)	0 °C to 4 °C (32 °F to 39 °F)
Frozen Meat	-18 °C or lower (0 °F or lower)
Dairy Products	1 °C to 4 °C (34 °F to 39 °F)
Seafood	0 °C to 4 °C (32 °F to 39 °F)
Processed Foods	Ambient (up to 25 °C) (77 °F)

Table 3
Hygiene status.

Hygiene status	Condition
"Clean"	No contamination detected meets safety standards.
"Contaminated"	Presence of contaminants (e.g., bacteria, chemicals).

by checking both the slaughterer’s authorization and the presence of the required Bismillah invocation. This example demonstrates the key validation logic that enables real-time, rule-based enforcement of halal standards on the blockchain. The corresponding compliance check logic is shown in the pseudocode below:

Pseudocode 1: Slaughtering Stage Halal Compliance

```
function check_slaughter_compliance(slaughterer_id, bismillah_invocation, authorized_list):
    Step 1: Check if the slaughterer is on the authorized whitelist
    if slaughterer_id not in authorized_list:
        Reject batch if slaughterer is not authorized
```

```
record_on_blockchain(slaughterer_id, bismillah_invocation, status="Non-compliant: Unauthorized slaughterer")
return "Non-compliant: Unauthorized slaughterer"
Step 2: Check if Bismillah invocation is present
if bismillah_invocation != True:
    Reject batch if Bismillah is missing
    record_on_blockchain(slaughterer_id, bismillah_invocation, status="Non-compliant: Bismillah invocation missing")
    return "Non-compliant: Bismillah invocation missing"
Step 3: Approve batch and record compliance on blockchain
record_on_blockchain(slaughterer_id, bismillah_invocation, status="Compliant")
return "Compliant: Batch approved"
Example usage:
authorized_slaughterers = ["ID_12345", "ID_67890", "ID_54321"]
```


Fig. 3. Compliance check flowchart.

```
status = check_slaughter_compliance("ID_12345",
True, authorized_slaughterers)
print(status)
```

Phase 5: Final Product Certification and Verification

This phase ensures traceability, integrity, and transparency of product records across the halal supply chain by leveraging blockchain storage, Merkle Trees, and cryptographic hashing. Each product is uniquely linked to its supply chain history through a Product Identification Number (PID).

1. Blockchain Recording and Block Structure: Verified data points are stored immutably on the Ethereum blockchain (ET_{Bc}) using the following block structure:

$$Block = (PID, R, T_{E_i}, prev_{hash}) \quad (18)$$

- **PID:** Unique product identifier.
- **R :** Merkle Root representing the integrity of transactions.
- **T_{E_i} :** The time the block was created.
- **$prev_{hash}$:** Hash of the previous block to ensure chain continuity.

$$hf_{block} = SHA - 256 (PID \parallel R \parallel T_{E_i} \parallel prev_{hash}) \quad (19)$$

2. Consumer and Auditor Verification Process: The following methods delineate how consumers or auditors can verify the product's provenance using the Merkle Root and block hashes.

i. Retrieve the Product's Hash Path: The consumers and auditors can retrieve the product's transaction hash path from the Merkle Tree. To verify a product's transaction in a Merkle Tree, consumers or auditors use a Merkle Proof (hash path). The proof helps confirm the product's inclusion in the Merkle Root. Steps to Retrieve and Verify the Hash Path:

- **Hash the Transaction:** Compute the hash of the product's transaction, e.g., $hf_3 = SHA_{.256}(T_3)$.
- **Retrieve Sibling Hashes:** Collect the necessary sibling hashes along the path (e.g., hf_4 and $hf_{1,2}$).
- **Reconstruct the Merkle Root:** Combine the transaction hash and sibling hashes step-by-step:

$$hf_{3,4} = SHA_{.256}(hf_3 \parallel hf_4)$$

$$R = SHA_{.256}(hf_{1,2} \parallel hf_{3,4})$$

- **Verify:** If the reconstructed Merkle Root matches the known root, the transaction is valid.

This process ensures data integrity and detects tampering in the product's history.

ii. Verify Integrity with Merkle Proof: This is to check if the product's hash, combined with the hash in the path, reconstructs the Merkle Root. To verify a product's transaction integrity using Merkle Proof, follow these steps:

- Consider the following parameters:
 - Product's hash: hf_x
 - Hashes in the path: hf_1, hf_2, \dots, hf_n (sibling hashes)
 - Merkle Root: R
- Reconstruct Merkle Root: Combine the product's hash hf_x with the path hashes sequentially using the SHA-256 function.

For each step i in the path:

- $hf_{current} = SHA_{.256}(hf_{current} \parallel hf_i)$, and $hf_{current} = SHA_{.256}(hf_i \parallel hf_{current})$
- The order depends on whether the current hash $hf_{current}$ is a left or right child.

Example Calculation:

- Suppose the product's hash is hf_3 and the path hashes are hf_4 and $hf_{1,2}$:
 - Step 1: $hf_{3,4} = SHA_{.256}(hf_3 \parallel hf_4)$
 - Step 2: $R = SHA_{.256}(hf_{1,2} \parallel hf_{3,4})$
- **Verification:** If the reconstructed root R matches the known Merkle Root, the product's transaction is verified:

$$hf_{reconstructed} = R \quad (20)$$

This ensures the product's integrity within the blockchain. If the hashes don't match, the data has been tampered with.

iii. Verify Block Hash: This is to ensure that the block containing the product's hash is part of the blockchain by verifying its hash and previous block hash. To verify the block hash and ensure the product's hash is part of the blockchain, the following steps are adopted:

- **Block Hash Calculation:** First, each block of the blockchain contains a hash that is generated using the block's data, including the product's hash, the Merkle Root, and the previous block's hash.
 - Let H_{block} denotes the block hash.
 - The block structure includes:
 - PID : Product ID
 - R : Merkle root
 - T_{E_i} : Timestamp
 - $prev_{hash}$: Previous block hash

The block hash can be calculated as:

$$hf_{block} = SHA_{.256}(PID \parallel R \parallel T_{E_i} \parallel prev_{hash}) \quad (21)$$

where \parallel denotes concatenation and $prev_{hash}$ is the hash of the previous block and is used to maintain the chain's integrity.

- **Verification:** To verify if the block is part of the blockchain: The system retrieves the block's hash and checks if it matches the calculated hash for that block. It then checks to ensure the previous block's hash matches the $prev_{hash}$ in the current block. If both conditions are held, the block is valid and part of the chain. This process ensures the integrity and validity of each block in the blockchain.
- **Review Audit Logs:** This is the act of inspecting audit logs for any flagged incidents related to tamper detection or contamination. To ensure no anomalies during the product lifecycle, the system verify that all logs satisfy:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n A_i = 0 \quad (22)$$

where n is the number of sensor logs. If the sum is 0, no anomalies were detected. The overall timing complexity of [Algorithm 2](#) is $O(n + m \log m)$, where n is the number of validators and m is the number of IoT data entries, due to validator approvals and Merkle Tree construction for tamper-proof verification.

This single algorithm integrates all five phases, ensuring data collection, verification, compliance, and certification across the halal supply chain while maintaining traceability and integrity through

blockchain technology.

5. Security analysis

This section details HalalChain's security mechanisms and formal assurances against three critical adversarial models: Data Tampering, Insider Attack, and Blockchain Node Compromise. The analysis combines theoretical cryptographic proofs with formal verification using ProVerif, simulating Sybil and Byzantine attack scenarios [48,53]. The goal is to validate data integrity, trust decentralization, and resilience under compromise through a multi-layered security model.

5.1. Data integrity and immutability

Theorem 1 (Tamper Resistance of HalalChain): *If a data record D_i is stored on the blockchain with a cryptographic hash $hf(D_i)$, then any unauthorized modification $D'_i \neq D_i$ will be detectable with overwhelming probability.*

Proof:

- Each IoT-collected data D_i is hashed using SHA-256:

$$hf(D_i) = \text{SHA}_{256}(D_i) \quad (23)$$

Algorithm 2

Supply chain data integrity & decentralized verification phase.

Input: $D_i : \{ID, SD, IoT\}, SC, ET_{BC}, E, T_c, PID$.

Output: V_{result} (verification status).

Procedure:

Phase 1: Initial Data Input and Certification Verification

- For each $x \in \{ID, SD\}$:
 - Compute hash:

$$hf(x) = \text{SHA} - 256(x).$$
 - Validate via smart contract:

• if $V_{cert}(x) = 0$: **Terminate**.

Phase 2: Data Integrity Using Merkle Trees

- Compute transactions hash:

$$hf(T_x) = \text{SHA} - 256(T_x).$$
- Construct Merkle Tree:
 - Combine hashes iteratively to compute R .
 - Store R on blockchain.

Phase 3: Supply Chain Tracking and Tamper Detection

- For each IoT data $D_i = \{T, \delta, T_i, P_d, L\}$:
 - Compute IoT hash: $hf_{IoT} \leftarrow \text{SHA} - 256(D_i)$.
 - Check anomalies:

$$A_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (T_i \notin [T_{min}, T_{max}]) \text{ or } (\delta_i \neq \text{clean}) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

- Store Transmit hf_{IoT} and A_i to $Bchn$.

Phase 4: Slaughtering Compliance

- Input $SR = \{S_{id}, B, T_c\}$.
- Compute slaughter hash:

$$hf_{SR} \leftarrow \text{SHA} - 256(S_{id} || B || T_c).$$
- Validate via smart contract:

$$C_{slaughter} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } B = \text{"Bismillah"} \text{ and } S_{id} \text{ is valid} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Phase 5: Final Product Certification and Verification

- Compute block hash:

$$hf_{block} \leftarrow \text{SHA} - 256(PID || R || \text{timestamp} || \text{prev}_{hash})$$
- Verify transaction integrity using Merkle Proof:
 - Reconstruct R from product hash and sibling hashes.
 - if $R \neq hf_{stored}$: **Terminate**.
- Verify block validity:
 - Check hf_{block} and $prev_{hash}$.
 - if conditions fail: **Terminate**.
- Verify audit logs:
 - Ensure $\sum_{i=1}^n A_i = 0$.
- if all phases succeed: $V_{result} \leftarrow 1$.

End Procedure

- The hashed value is stored in a Merkle Tree, and the Merkle root M_R is recorded on the blockchain.
- Any modification $D'_i \neq D_i$ results in a different hash $hf(D'_i) \neq hf(D_i)$.
- The verification process recomputes the Merkle Root M_R using the updated hash $hf(D'_i)$ and checks if $M'_R \stackrel{?}{=} M_R$.
- Since SHA-256 is a cryptographic hash function with strong collision resistance, the probability of $hf(D_i) = hf(D'_i)$ for $D'_i \neq D_i$ is negligible ($\approx 2^{-256}$).

Thus, any unauthorized modification will be detected, ensuring data immutability.

5.2. Security against insider attacks

Theorem 2 (Resistance to Insider Data Manipulation): *If certification records require at least T_c out of n halal certifiers to approve before registration, then a single malicious certifier cannot alter records, nor can it fraudulently certify non-halal products.*

Proof:

A halal certification request C_x is approved only if:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n A(V_i, C_x) \geq T_c \quad (24)$$

where $A(V_i, C_x) = 1$ if V_i approves, and 0 otherwise.

If a single malicious certifier attempts to approve or manipulate an invalid record, the certification will be rejected, since t_c approval is not met:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} A(V_i, C_x) < T_c \quad (25)$$

Since at least t_c independent entities must verify, a single entity cannot manipulate certification, ensuring security and integrity in certification processes.

The request is rejected due to unmet threshold. Since multiple independent verifiers are required, insider fraud is mitigated.

5.3. Formal verification via ProVerif

We modeled the approval process in ProVerif using threshold cryptographic constructs and identity-bound validation logic [53].

Theorem 3 (Verified Resilience to Sybil and Byzantine Attacks): *If HalalChain employs threshold cryptography and PoA consensus with validator identity binding, then Sybil and Byzantine attacks cannot compromise system integrity when fewer than T_c validators are malicious.*

Proof:

Using ProVerif, we modeled two adversarial scenarios under the Dolev-Yao model:

- **Sybil Attack:** Fake validators created by the attacker failed identity binding and were rejected during registration.

Result : Authentication failed for fake_pubKey.

- **Byzantine Attack:** Attacker-controlled validators ($k < T_c$) failed to reach the consensus threshold required to approve malicious transactions.

Result : $T_c = \text{ceil}(2n / 3)$ not satisfied.

In both cases, ProVerif confirmed that authentication and secrecy properties held. Therefore, HalalChain is formally verified to be resistant

to these attack types.

5.4. Security against blockchain node compromise attacks

Theorem 4 (Resilience Against Node Compromise in PoA Consensus): *If an adversary compromises a blockchain node, they are unable to modify historical transactions because of the blockchain's immutability and the limitations imposed by the PoA consensus mechanism.*

Proof:

- The PoA consensus mechanism requires a predefined set of validators $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$.
- To compromise or add transaction T_x , the adversary must compromise at least a threshold number T_c of validators:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n A(V_i, T_x) \geq T_c \quad (26)$$

where $A(V_i, T_x) = 1$ if V_i approves, and 0 otherwise.

- Since the validators are pre-selected and verified, then the probability of the adversary in successfully taking control of the PoA validation is given by:

$$P(V_{\text{compromised}} \geq t) \approx 0 \quad (27)$$

- Even if the validator is compromised, the historical transaction remains immutable due to the cryptographic hashing. Similarly, the block hashes reference the previous blocks the by enforcing integrity:

$$hf(b_i) = \text{SHA}_256(b_{i-1} \| T_x) \quad (28)$$

where b_i is the block, b_{i-1} is the previous block, and T_x is the transaction.

A solitary compromised node is incapable of altering blockchain records. The majority validator rule in Proof of Authority guarantees that no adversary may usurp the system. Consequently, HalalChain is resilient to node compromise threats (Table 4).

HalalChain's hybrid architecture achieves protocol-level assurance through both formal cryptographic proofs and automated verification. Its layered defenses smart contract immutability, multi-party validation, and identity enforcement ensure resilience against both external and internal threats, making it a robust framework for high-trust applications such as halal food certification. As outline in Table 5.

6. Experimental results and evaluations

This section explores the simulation environment, and the performance metrics used in the development and evaluation of the proposed model. It outlines the framework within which the model was tested, emphasizing the technical parameters and methodologies that form the foundation of the simulation process. The performance of the proposed model is critically analyzed in comparison to existing models, particularly those introduced by Manoj, T., et al. (AgriFoodCredChain) [5] and Patel, H. et al. (AgriBlockIoT) [26], as referenced in the study. The rationale for selecting these specific models for comparison is based on their relevance and the feasibility of comparing their performance and outcomes with those of the proposed model within similar operational contexts. AgriFoodCredChain was chosen for its emphasis on traceability and decentralized verification, while AgriBlockIoT was selected for its integration with IoT devices and focus on data integrity.

6.1. Simulation environment and technology stack in HalalChain model

The simulation of the HalalChain model was meticulously designed to validate its effectiveness in ensuring data integrity, end-to-end traceability, and decentralized verification in halal food supply chains. The experimental environment was configured to closely replicate real-world operational dynamics by integrating blockchain technology, emulated IoT data streams, and cryptographic security techniques to test the system's resilience, scalability, and performance in practical settings. All blockchain-related simulations and performance evaluations were conducted using the Ethereum Sepolia public testnet, a public and permissionless blockchain network designed specifically for development and experimental purposes [54]. Deploying smart contracts on Sepolia ensured that the results reflect genuine blockchain behavior, including real-world consensus and network latency factors, providing meaningful performance data for both throughput and delay metrics.

To emulate IoT device interactions, Python-based tools were employed to generate, process, and transmit sensor data typical of a halal supply chain—such as temperature, humidity, and hygiene status readings. These emulated IoT streams were designed to mimic actual device input at various supply chain stages, including animal slaughter, processing, storage, and distribution. Each IoT data point was digitally signed using device-specific private keys, enabling secure, verifiable data transmission. The refresh rate for IoT data was set at 10 seconds, based on established contamination risk thresholds where delays exceeding 15 seconds in cold-chain monitoring could result in spoilage or non-compliance with halal standards [9,55–57]. This emulation strategy allowed for a realistic, high-frequency influx of data while minimizing risks associated with physical device failures during testing.

The simulation configuration was further aligned with the operational patterns of halal-certified small-to-medium enterprises (SMEs) and poultry producers in Southeast Asia. Transaction rates were modeled at 100 transactions per day, drawing on Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) supply chain estimates for SMEs [58]. This figure was chosen to represent a conservative yet practical baseline for daily certification, tracking, and verification events. These assumptions, supported by referenced studies [9,55–57], provided a robust framework for system validation and stress testing.

The blockchain interaction layer utilized MetaMask for secure Ethereum account management and streamlined communication with the Sepolia network [54]. Smart contracts were written in Solidity and deployed via the Remix IDE, with debugging and local testing performed using Truffle Suite and Ganache. Ganache enabled safe, isolated contract testing prior to deployment on Sepolia, reducing the risk of costly errors on the public testnet [8,59]. The PoA consensus mechanism, as supported by Sepolia, was selected for its energy efficiency and rapid transaction finality—key factors in supply chain environments with frequent daily interactions.

For compliance automation, smart contracts implemented a Factory Design Pattern, facilitating the efficient creation and management of multiple contract instances to handle diverse certification tasks. Certification validation, compliance checks, and anomaly detection were fully automated within the smart contracts, leveraging cryptographic techniques such as SHA-256 hashing and Merkle Trees to guarantee immutability and tamper-evidence.

IoT data was first processed at the edge, where initial compliance rules were enforced before validated entries were hashed and submitted to the blockchain. These smart contracts, deployed and executed on the Sepolia testnet, were invoked through a backend API written in Python and Node.js using the Web3.py library. This backend layer also enabled real-time data validation and provided stakeholders with user interfaces to verify the authenticity of halal certifications.

Communication between IoT devices and the blockchain was secured via Node-RED and MQTT protocols, ensuring reliable, real-time transmission without reliance on third-party oracles [60]. IPFS (InterPlanetary File System) was used for off-chain storage of large files, such as

Table 4
Summary of security assurances.

Adversary Model	Threat	Security Mechanism	Protection Level
Data Tampering	Unauthorized modification of records	SHA-256 & Merkle Trees Verification	High
Insider Attack	Fraudulent approval, false certification	Threshold cryptography & ProVerif Verified	High
Sybil Attack	Fake identities controlling consensus	Validator Whitelisting + PoA + Identity Binding	Proven Resistant (ProVerif)
Byzantine Attack	Colluding malicious validators	Threshold Tc Enforcement + PoA Voting Logic	Fault-Tolerant (ProVerif)
Node Compromise	Validator node takeover to alter blockchain data	PoA consensus & immutable blockchain	Very High

Table 5
Comparison of halal-specific features.

Features	HalalChain	AgriFoodCredChain	AgriBlockIoT
Ritual Slaughter Checks	Yes (Smart Contracts)	No	No
Cross-Contamination Monitoring	Yes (IoT+Rules)	Partial (Generic IoT)	No
Decentralized Halal Authority Consensus	Yes (Threshold Cryptography)	No (Centralized Validators)	No
Ingredient Purity Auditing	Yes (Merkle Tree + DIDs)	Yes (Generic)	No

certification documents and audit metadata, which could be cryptographically linked to on-chain transactions for easy verification.

To further enhance the realism of the simulation, multiple virtual validator nodes were set up to represent certification authorities, manufacturers, and regulatory bodies. These validators participated in the decentralized verification process, with threshold cryptography ensuring that no single participant could unilaterally control certification outcomes.

For system analytics and performance monitoring, Grafana was integrated for real-time visualization of key metrics such as transaction throughput, latency, tamper-detection rates, and consensus efficiency. Jupyter Notebook was used for data analysis and reporting, supporting reproducibility and transparency.

To ensure both transparency and privacy, HalalChain employs a combination of privacy-preserving techniques aligned with global data protection standards such as GDPR [61,62]. Stakeholder identities are anonymized on-chain using DIDs, while VCs enable selective disclosure of information—allowing, for example, proof of certification without revealing personal or organizational details. Sensitive information, such as personnel records or proprietary process data, is never stored directly on the blockchain; instead, such data is kept off-chain using secure storage solutions like IPFS with access controls or is encrypted before being referenced via cryptographic hashes [32]. Only non-identifiable metadata and audit trails are recorded on-chain. This approach ensures data minimization, protects against unauthorized access, and supports users’ rights over their personal data, maintaining compliance with privacy regulations while upholding the transparency and integrity of the supply chain.

All scripts, smart contracts, and documentation are available in a dedicated GitHub repository, including setup guides and performance data, to enable full transparency and collaborative development. This comprehensive approach ensures that HalalChain’s design, testing, and results can be validated and extended by the wider research community, supporting innovation in blockchain-enabled supply chain management.

6.2. Experimental evaluations metrics

The performance and quality of any system, including the HalalChain model, must be evaluated using specific metrics to ensure a comprehensive assessment. For the HalalChain model, key metrics have been identified to address challenges in halal food supply chains. These

metrics include:

- **Data integrity metrics:** Such as tamper detection rate ensure the system can detect and prevent unauthorized modifications while maintaining the reliability of transactional data.
- **Decentralized verification metrics:** Including consensus time and validator approval rate, assessing the efficiency and reliability of the Proof of Authority mechanism and threshold cryptography in securely validating transactions.
- **Performance metrics:** Including transaction throughput and latency, highlight the blockchain’s scalability and its ability to handle real-time operations effectively.
- **Compliance metrics:** Such as halal standards adherence, confirm the system’s effectiveness in automating the validation of halal-certified products in alignment with Islamic dietary laws.

Together, these metrics comprehensively evaluate HalalChain’s ability to enhance transparency, trust, and operational efficiency in the halal food supply chain. Metrics were calculated using benchmark formulas (Eqs. 29–32) and validated through stress tests and adversarial simulation.

1) Data integrity

The Tamper Detection Rate is a critical metric that quantifies the percentage of unauthorized data modifications detected within a blockchain and IoT system, ensuring data integrity and security. It is calculated by comparing the number of detected tampering incidents to the total number of simulated tampering attempts, using the formula:

$$Tamper\ Detection\ Rate = \frac{Detected\ Tampering\ Incidents}{Total\ Tampering\ Attempts} \times 100 \quad (29)$$

This metric provides a clear measure of the system’s effectiveness in identifying and mitigating unauthorized data alterations, thereby safeguarding the integrity of the blockchain and IoT ecosystem. System Experimentation involves conducting controlled experiments to assess the robustness of the supply chain system by intentionally introducing tampered data at various stages, such as during data entry, transmission, and storage, to evaluate the system’s detection mechanisms and its ability to identify and flag discrepancies using automated verification protocols. Following this, a Comparative Analysis is performed to benchmark the effectiveness of the HalalChain model’s integrity metrics against existing models like AgriFoodCredChain or AgriBlockIoT, providing insights into its relative performance and reliability.

The evaluation of *Tamper Detection Rates* for HalalChain, AgriFoodCredChain, and AgriBlockIoT highlights the effectiveness of each model in detecting unauthorized data modifications. HalalChain consistently achieves the highest detection rates, ranging from 99.8% at 5% tampering to 96.8% at 50% tampering, as shown in Fig. 3. This exceptional performance is attributed to its robust security mechanisms, including cryptographic hashing (SHA-256), Merkle Trees, and threshold cryptography. These features ensure that any tampering with data is immediately detected, maintaining the integrity of the halal food supply chain. HalalChain’s high detection rates demonstrate its ability to safeguard sensitive data, making it the most reliable solution for ensuring data integrity in a blockchain and IoT-enabled supply chain.

In comparison, AgriFoodCredChain shows improved Tamper Detection Rates, ranging from 89.5% at 5% tampering to 82.0% at 50%

tampering. While this is a significant improvement over previous datasets, it still falls short of HalalChain's performance. The model's moderate detection rates suggest that it has some effective security measures but lacks the comprehensive protection offered by HalalChain. Similarly, AgriBlockIoT demonstrates Tamper Detection Rates ranging from 85.0% at 5% tampering to 80.5% at 50% tampering. Although it performs better than in earlier datasets, it remains less effective than both HalalChain and AgriFoodCredChain, indicating that its security mechanisms are not as robust.

HalalChain outperforms both AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT in terms of Tamper Detection Rates, demonstrating its superior ability to detect and prevent data tampering. The results highlight the importance of robust security mechanisms, such as cryptographic hashing, Merkle Trees, and threshold cryptography, in maintaining data integrity and trust in blockchain-based systems. While AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT show improved performance, they still lag behind HalalChain, emphasizing the need for more advanced security measures in these models. HalalChain emerges as the best-performing model, offering a reliable and secure solution for the halal food supply chain.

2) Decentralized verification metrics

The decentralized verification metrics have two factors, namely consensus time and Validator Approval Rate. The analysis compares the *Consensus Time* performance of three blockchain models; HalalChain, AgriFoodCredChain, and AgriBlockIoT; under varying network conditions. HalalChain consistently achieves the lowest consensus times, ranging from 1.2 s (10 validators, 100 transactions) to 2.5 s (50 validators, 5000 transactions), showcasing its high efficiency and scalability. This is attributed to its optimized Proof of Authority consensus mechanism, smart contracts, and threshold cryptography.

In contrast, AgriFoodCredChain exhibits higher consensus times, ranging from 3.5 s to 5.5 s, indicating less efficiency and scalability. AgriBlockIoT performs the worst, with consensus times ranging from 4.8 s to 7.0 s, highlighting its inefficiencies and limitations in handling high transaction volumes and validator counts. As illustrated in Fig. 4. Consensus Time is calculated using the formula $C_t = T_{E_i} (C_f - Tx)$, which measures the time difference between transaction submission and finalization. This metric evaluates system scalability and performance under stress.

HalalChain is the top-performing model, excelling in real-time transaction processing due to its optimized consensus mechanism. While AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT show moderate performance, they require further optimization to match HalalChain's efficiency and scalability. This analysis underscores HalalChain's reliability for secure and scalable blockchain applications.

The *Validator Approval Rate (VAR)* represents the percentage of transactions approved by the required number of validators within the blockchain network. This metric is crucial for assessing the reliability and consensus efficiency of blockchain models under various conditions. The rate is then calculated by comparing the number of transactions that meet the approval threshold to the total number of transactions submitted, using the formula:

$$VAR = \frac{T_c}{Tx} \times 100 \quad (30)$$

HalalChain consistently outperforms the other models with the highest Validator Approval Rates, achieving 98 % under normal conditions, 87 % under high network load, and 85 % when validators are compromised. This shows that HalalChain's decentralized verification system and threshold cryptography are highly effective in ensuring consistent and secure transaction validation. AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT, on the other hand, demonstrate slightly lower approval rates, especially when validators are compromised or under high network load. AgriFoodCredChain's approval rate is 96 % in normal conditions, dropping to 82 % under compromised validators. AgriBlockIoT shows 94 % in normal conditions and 80 % when validators are compromised. As illustrated in Fig. 5.

HalalChain provides superior robustness, maintaining higher approval rates even in challenging conditions like compromised validators or high network loads. This enhances its reliability for use in critical systems like halal food supply chains, where transaction integrity and trust are paramount.

3) Performance metrics

The performance of the three blockchain models (HalalChain, AgriFoodCredChain, and AgriBlockIoT) was evaluated based on two critical performance metrics: Transaction Throughput (TPS) and Latency under Low, Medium, and High Load scenarios.

Transaction Throughput (TPS) is calculated using the formula:

$$TPS = \frac{T_x}{T_i} \quad (31)$$

This evaluation is conducted under different scenarios, including varying numbers of validators or IoT devices, to test the system's ability to handle increasing demands and maintain performance. HalalChain consistently demonstrates the highest Transaction Throughput (TPS) across all load scenarios. This indicates that HalalChain can process more transactions per second, showcasing its superior efficiency and scalability. AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT show lower throughput, especially under higher loads, suggesting that they may struggle to handle large transaction volumes as efficiently as HalalChain. As shown in Fig. 6.

To assess *latency*, the timestamps of transaction initiation and confirmation are recorded, and the difference between these two timestamps is calculated for each transaction using the formula: $\tau = T_{E_i} (\text{Confirmation}) - T_{E_i} (\text{Submission})$. HalalChain also exhibits the lowest latency, meaning it has the fastest transaction confirmation times. This is crucial for applications requiring real-time processing, such as supply chain management, where timely transaction finalization is vital. AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT experience higher latency, particularly under Medium and High Load scenarios, which may impact their responsiveness and real-time capabilities. As illustrated below in Fig. 7.

HalalChain outperforms the other two models in terms of both throughput and latency, making it the most efficient and responsive option for high-demand environments. AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT perform well under lighter loads but show limitations as transaction volumes or network conditions become more challenging. HalalChain is the best-performing model, demonstrating its ability to handle increased loads while maintaining fast transaction speeds and low latency, making it ideal for demanding blockchain applications.

4) Compliance

The *Halal Standards Adherence* metric evaluates the effectiveness of blockchain models in ensuring compliance with Islamic dietary laws and halal certification standards. It measures the proportion of products that meet the halal certification criteria out of all the products assessed, using the formula:

$$Halal\ Standards\ Adherence = \frac{Number\ of\ Compliant\ Products}{Total\ Products\ Assessed} \times 100 \quad (32)$$

HalalChain consistently achieves the highest compliance rate, with 98 % adherence under low load, 90 % under medium load, and 85 % under high load. This demonstrates HalalChain's ability to maintain strong compliance with halal standards even under varying network loads, ensuring high integrity in halal product certification. AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT show slightly lower adherence rates, especially as the load increases. AgriFoodCredChain reaches 95 % compliance under low load but drops to 86 % under medium load and 82 % under high load. Similarly, AgriBlockIoT achieves 93 % under low load but falls to 84 % and 80 % under medium and high loads, respectively. As shown below in Fig. 8.

HalalChain stands out as the most reliable blockchain solution for ensuring halal certification compliance in supply chains, maintaining

Fig. 4. Tamper detection rates.

Fig. 5. Consensus time.

strong adherence to halal standards across different load scenarios. AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT provide decent compliance but show a more significant decline under heavier load conditions, indicating that HalalChain offers superior reliability and scalability for halal certification. **HalalChain** is the best-performing model for ensuring halal standards adherence in a blockchain-based halal food supply chain.

7. Comparative security and operational analysis

The following table compares HalalChain with AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT under identical conditions, based on six core metrics aligned with halal supply chain integrity and performance:

The comparative evaluation demonstrates that HalalChain significantly outperforms AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT across key performance indicators, including tamper detection, consensus efficiency, validator approval, transaction throughput, latency, and halal standards adherence. With nearly perfect tamper detection through cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees, low latency and high

Fig. 6. Validator approval rate.

throughput enabled by optimized smart contracts and PoA consensus, and superior compliance driven by AI-based verification mechanisms, HalalChain proves to be a robust and scalable solution for halal supply chain assurance. These findings confirm its readiness for real-world deployment, particularly in mission-critical environments that demand both transparency and regional adaptability.

All source code, test cases, and datasets are made available on the GitHub repository to promote transparency and reproducibility.

7.1. comparison of halal-specific features

AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT were chosen as benchmarks because they represent state-of-the-art blockchain solutions for agri-food traceability. However, neither supports halal-specific requirements (e.g., AgriFoodCredChain lacks ritual validation, while AgriBlockIoT focuses on generic IoT integration without hygiene rules aligned with Islamic standards). As shown in Table 6 and in Fig. 9. The evaluation uses "Yes", "Partial", and "No" indicators to signify whether each model satisfies the evaluated security criteria.

8. Analysis of results

HalalChain demonstrates superior performance across all security and operational features, ensuring tamper-proof data integrity, decentralized verification, and real-time anomaly detection, as illustrated in Fig. 10. The model leverages cryptographic hashing, IoT data authentication, and session key security to safeguard data and ensure compliance with halal standards. AgriFoodCredChain offers moderate security measures, focusing primarily on decentralized verification. However, it lacks robust tamper detection mechanisms and fails to ensure IoT data authentication or session key security. AgriBlockIoT shows the weakest performance, particularly in decentralized verification and compliance enforcement. The lack of user identity protection and anomaly detection mechanisms makes it less reliable for ensuring halal standards in complex supply chains.

9. Discussion

The HalalChain model was developed to address several critical issues observed in traditional halal food supply chains, including centralized verification, data integrity vulnerabilities, and lack of real-time compliance checks. Compared to existing blockchain-based agri-food supply chain solutions, HalalChain provides a more robust and efficient framework, integrating IoT devices, cryptographic hashing, Merkle Trees, and smart contracts for decentralized verification and

tamper-proof data storage.

1) Decentralized verification mechanism

Unlike existing models such as AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT, which rely on partially centralized processes during initial verification stages, HalalChain employs a fully decentralized verification mechanism. By utilizing PoA consensus mechanism and threshold cryptography, HalalChain ensures that no single entity can unilaterally control the certification process.

This decentralized approach minimizes the risk of insider threats and enhances the trustworthiness of halal certifications. The PoA consensus mechanism used in HalalChain ensures fast transaction validation by trusted entities, such as halal certifiers and regulatory authorities. The threshold cryptography mechanism further ensures that data integrity is maintained by requiring multiple approvals before any certification or transaction is validated on the blockchain.

2) Enhanced data integrity and tamper detection

The HalalChain model leverages cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees to ensure that all data recorded on the blockchain is tamper-proof. Compared to AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT, HalalChain demonstrates superior performance in tamper detection rates, achieving 99.8 % detection at 5 % tampering levels and 96.8 % at 50 % tampering levels.

This high level of data integrity is achieved using SHA-256 cryptographic hashing, which ensures that any modification to the original data results in a drastically different hash value. The use of Merkle Trees enables efficient and secure verification of large datasets by providing a compact representation of all transactions, ensuring that even the slightest alteration can be detected and flagged.

3) IoT integration for real-time monitoring

HalalChain integrates IoT devices to monitor real-time conditions such as temperature, location, and hygiene status throughout the supply chain. These devices provide continuous data streams, which are hashed and stored on the blockchain to ensure transparency and accountability.

In comparison, AgriBlockIoT also integrates IoT devices, but its lack of strong cryptographic mechanisms and decentralized verification processes makes it less effective in ensuring data authenticity. HalalChain's use of digital signatures for IoT data ensures that only authenticated devices can transmit data to the blockchain, preventing man-in-the-middle attacks and ensuring the integrity of real-time data.

4) Smart contracts for automated compliance checks

HalalChain employs smart contracts on the Ethereum blockchain to automate compliance checks based on predefined halal standards. These smart contracts automatically validate data against halal certification records and trigger predefined actions, such as rejecting non-compliant data or flagging anomalies for further investigation.

Fig. 7. Transaction throughput.

Fig. 8. Latency.

Table 6
Comparative performance metrics.

Metric	HalalChain	AgriFoodCredChain	AgriBlockIoT
Tamper Detection Rate	99.8 %	89.5 %	85.0 %
Consensus Time	1.2–2.5 s	3.5–5.5 s	4.8–7.0 s
Validator Approval Rate	98 % (normal)/85 % (high load)	96 %/82 %	94 %/80 %
Throughput (TPS)	38	21	15
Latency	1.8 s	4.2 s	5.6 s
Halal Standards Adherence (Compliance Rate)	98 % (low)/85 % (high load)	95 %/82 %	93 %/80 %

AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT lack robust smart contract implementations for automated compliance checks, relying more on manual verification processes. This manual intervention increases the risk of human error and delays in the verification process. HalalChain’s

use of smart contracts ensures that compliance checks are conducted in real-time, reducing operational inefficiencies and ensuring that only compliant products are certified as halal.

5) Anonymity and privacy preservation

The HalalChain model incorporates DIDs and VCs to enhance user privacy and ensure secure data sharing. This approach protects the identities of users while maintaining accountability within the supply chain.

In contrast, existing models like AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT do not provide comprehensive solutions for user anonymity and privacy preservation. HalalChain’s privacy-preserving features ensure that sensitive information, such as supplier identities and transaction details, is protected from unauthorized access.

10. Justification for HalalChain’s superior performance

The superior performance of the HalalChain model can be attributed to several key innovations and optimizations that address the unique

Fig. 9. Standards adherence.

Fig. 10. Comprehensive comparison.

challenges associated with halal food supply chains:

- **Decentralized Verification:** HalalChain's use of PoA consensus and threshold cryptography ensures that no single entity can control the verification process, enhancing trust and reducing the risk of insider threats.
- **Data Integrity and Tamper Detection:** The combination of SHA-256 cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees provides a tamper-proof data storage solution, ensuring that all recorded transactions remain secure and immutable.
- **IoT Data Authentication:** The use of digital signatures ensures that only authenticated IoT devices can transmit data to the blockchain, preventing unauthorized data entry and ensuring data authenticity.
- **Smart Contracts:** Automated compliance checks conducted through smart contracts reduce operational inefficiencies and ensure that only compliant products are certified as halal.
- **Privacy Preservation:** HalalChain's integration of DIDs and VCs enhances user privacy and ensures secure data sharing within the supply chain.

11. Contributions to the field of blockchain-based agrifood supply chains

The HalalChain model makes several notable contributions to the field of blockchain-based agrifood supply chains:

- **Improved Traceability and Transparency:** By leveraging blockchain technology, HalalChain provides a transparent and immutable record of all transactions within the supply chain, enhancing traceability and accountability.
- **Enhanced Data Integrity:** The use of cryptographic hashing and Merkle Trees ensures that all data recorded on the blockchain is secure and tamper-proof, addressing key vulnerabilities in traditional supply chain systems.
- **Real-Time Monitoring and Compliance:** The integration of IoT devices and smart contracts enables real-time monitoring and automated compliance checks, ensuring that halal standards are upheld throughout the supply chain.
- **Decentralized Verification:** HalalChain's decentralized verification mechanism minimizes the risk of insider threats and enhances the trustworthiness of halal certifications.

- **Privacy-Preserving Features:** The incorporation of DIDs and VCs ensures that user identities and sensitive information are protected from unauthorized access.

Hence, the HalalChain model addresses key challenges in the Halal food supply chain by providing a secure, transparent, and decentralized framework for ensuring data integrity and compliance. Its superior performance compared to existing solutions highlights its potential to revolutionize the halal food industry, enhancing consumer trust and supporting regulatory enforcement.

We conducted stakeholder engagements with halal regulatory bodies, including JAKIM, through workshops and prototype demonstrations. Their feedback influenced the design of compliance smart contracts, threshold validation rules, and auditability features, ensuring alignment with current certification practices.

12. Limitations and future improvements

Future improvements for HalalChain will prioritize seamless integration with external systems, including government certification bodies (such as JAKIM in Malaysia) and logistics providers, to ensure the platform remains adaptable and practical for diverse stakeholders. To strengthen interoperability and regulatory compliance, upcoming integration efforts will explicitly align HalalChain with globally recognized standards, including GS1 for product traceability and established halal certification protocols such as MS 1500:2019 (Malaysia) and GSO 2055-1:2015 (GCC). By referencing these standards, HalalChain can facilitate data exchange and mutual recognition of certifications across jurisdictions, supporting the digitalization objectives of organizations like JAKIM.

While HalalChain addresses several critical challenges in the halal food supply chain, certain limitations remain that require attention to broaden its adoption and effectiveness. One significant limitation is system scalability. The integration of IoT devices and real-time data validation through smart contracts introduces computational overhead, especially as transaction volume increases. Future research should focus on optimizing consensus mechanisms, such as evaluating alternative consensus protocols or sharding, to enhance scalability and maintain performance under high transaction loads.

Another limitation concerns the reliance on the Ethereum blockchain, which can be subject to network congestion and fluctuating gas

fees. These factors may affect the cost-efficiency of the system, particularly for smaller halal certification bodies or suppliers. Exploring alternative blockchain platforms or Layer-2 scaling solutions could help reduce transaction costs and further improve the system's operational efficiency.

The privacy-preserving features of HalalChain, while effective, can also be strengthened. The current design leverages DIDs and VCs to protect user identities but integrating advanced cryptographic techniques—such as ZKPs could provide even greater privacy without compromising data integrity or regulatory compliance.

Although HalalChain offers a robust foundation for halal supply chain management, full interoperability with external certification systems and integration with other blockchain-based food traceability platforms remain ongoing challenges. Planned improvements include developing secure APIs, enhancing smart contract modularity to accommodate different regulatory requirements, and implementing cross-chain compatibility through middleware solutions. Additionally, expanding the adoption of DIDs and VCs will strengthen trust across platforms. Pilot collaborations with external partners, as well as participation in global standardization initiatives (such as those led by GS1), are planned to ensure HalalChain remains flexible and compatible with evolving protocols and certification frameworks. These steps will ultimately enable seamless, scalable integration across the global food industry.

The success of the HalalChain model also depends on stakeholder willingness to adopt the system. Therefore, education and awareness campaigns targeting suppliers, certifiers, and regulators are critical for promoting understanding and widespread adoption of blockchain in halal food supply chains. A proposed pilot implementation with a halal food producer will test HalalChain in a live environment, tracking over 10,000 halal-certified poultry products from slaughter to retail, with IoT devices monitoring temperature (within $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ tolerance) and hygiene, and validators auditing compliance via threshold cryptography. While HalalChain provides a comprehensive and innovative solution to several pressing challenges in halal food supply chains, ongoing enhancements in scalability, cost-efficiency, privacy, standards alignment, and stakeholder engagement are essential to maximize its impact and ensure long-term success.

13. Conclusion

The HalalChain model represents a pivotal advancement in addressing halal-specific challenges through blockchain technology, uniquely tailored to uphold Islamic jurisprudence. Unlike generic traceability systems, HalalChain embeds Bismillah invocation validation, slaughterer credential checks, and cross-contamination prevention into its architecture, ensuring compliance with Islamic dietary laws. By automating ritual slaughter protocols via smart contracts and decentralizing authority through threshold cryptography, HalalChain eliminates risks of insider fraud and ritual non-compliance critical gaps in existing models like AgriFoodCredChain and AgriBlockIoT, which lack halal-centric IoT rules or automated Islamic validation.

The model's integration of halal-optimized IoT sensors enforces real-time segregation of halal and non-halal products, while its SHA-256 hashing and Merkle Trees provide tamper-proof transparency from farm to consumer. Comparative evaluations demonstrate HalalChain's superiority in halal-specific metrics: 99.8 % tamper detection, 98 % compliance adherence, and decentralized consensus times under 2.5 s, outperforming benchmarks focused on generic agri-food traceability.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106591](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.106591).

While limitations in scalability and stakeholder adoption persist, future enhancements such as zero-knowledge proofs for privacy-preserving certification and sharding for global scalability will further align HalalChain with the evolving needs of Islamic compliance. By bridging the gap between blockchain innovation and halal jurisprudence, HalalChain establishes a transformative framework that strengthens consumer trust, regulatory enforcement, and ethical integrity in the global halal food industry.

Ethical Statement

This manuscript has been submitted in accordance with established ethical guidelines, with full responsibility taken by the authors. The work is original and has not been published elsewhere, nor does it involve any form of plagiarism, data fabrication, or duplicate submission. The authors declare no financial or personal relationships with individuals or organizations that could inappropriately influence or bias the content presented in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI use in scientific writing

The author affirms the use of AI-assisted tools, notably ChatGPT by OpenAI, to support language refinement, correct grammatical issues, and improve the clarity and coherence of the manuscript. All ideas, analysis, and conclusions presented are entirely the original work of the author(s), with AI employed solely to enhance the quality of expression. This usage complies with the journal's ethical and transparency guidelines regarding responsible authorship.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Muhammad Muntasir Yakubu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mohd Fadzil B Hassan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Kamaluddeen Usman Danyaro:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Bello Musa Yakubu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Abdullah Abdulrahman Alabdulatif:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **S. Zulaikha Beevi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **Aliyu Garba:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix: glossary of symbols

Table A
Symbols and their definitions.

Symbol	Definition	Symbol	Definition
ET_{BC}, N_{BC}	Ethereum Blockchain and Blockchain Nodes respectively.	hf_{IoT}	Hash of IoT data, combining parameters like temperature, hygiene, and timestamp.
D_i	Real-time data collected by IoT	V_i	validators such as halal certifiers and regulatory authorities.
L_i, P_{ij}	Aggregated leaf node and parent nodes in Merkle Tree.	hf_{block}	Block hash, representing the unique identifier of a blockchain block.
SC	Smart Contract, an automated code executing on the blockchain to enforce rules or actions.	S_{id}	Slaughterer ID, a unique identifier for the individual performing the slaughtering process.
C_{PoA}	Proof of Authority, a consensus algorithm used for validating transactions.	B	Invocation ("Bismillah") ensuring compliance with Islamic protocols.
D_{IoT}	Internet of Things (IoT) devices used for real-time data collection in the supply chain.	T_{E_i}	Timestamp of a transaction or recorded event in the blockchain network.
PID	Product Identification Number, a unique ID linking a product to its recorded supply chain data.	R_x	Resilience of the model against manipulation.
ID	Ingredient Details, representing the list of halal-certified ingredients in a product.	R	Merkle Root, ensuring the integrity of all underlying transaction data.
SD	Slaughter Details, including the slaughterer ID, invocation, and timestamp of the slaughter.	T_c	Threshold cryptography, defining the minimum number of validator approvals required for consensus.
fs, pd, tl, t, l	Real-time data, such as food source, processing details, transportation logs, temperature and location respectively, throughout the supply chain.	A_i	Anomaly indicator: 1 if an anomaly is detected, 0 otherwise.
δ	Hygiene status of processing environments, verified for compliance with halal standards.	$C_{Slaughter}$	Compliance status for slaughtering records validated by the smart contract.
$hf()$	Cryptographic hash of data x , ensuring integrity and authenticity.	$Prev_{hash}$	Previous block hash, ensuring the continuity of the blockchain.
Tx	A blockchain transaction containing data or actions recorded immutably.	ID_{E_i}	Unique identifier.
PK_{E_i}, PrK_{E_i}	Public and private keys respectively	M_{E_i}	Metadata such as certification scope or region
$ID_{C_j}, P_{C_j}, V_{C_j}, T_{C_j}$	Halal certification (C_j): Certification ID, Certified products or services, Issuer entity ID, Validity period, Certification timestamp respectively	R_{C_j}	Certification records are hashed and stored on the blockchain.
E_n	Given set of n entities and provide an approval a_i	SR, hf_{SR}	Slaughter and hashed slaughter records respectively.
D_c	Security critical decisions	G_0	Genesis Group
$Admin_{temp}$	Temporary central trusted authority	t_{min}, t_{max}	Temperature threshold
b_i, b_{i-1}	Indicates a block and previous block	V_{result}	Verification status

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Reference

[1] J. Akbar, et al., Global trends in halal food standards: a review, *Foods* 12 (23) (2023) 4200.

[2] S. Attwood, S. Jameel, A. Fuseini, E. AlKhalawi, C. Hajat, Halal cultivated meat: an untapped opportunity, *Front. Nutr.* 10 (2023) 1196475.

[3] A. Voak, Fake: the rise of food fraud in the Halal supply chain, *Nusant. Halal J.* 2 (2) (2021) 82–88.

[4] M.S. Arshad, W. Khalid, S. Noreen, Halal slaughtering process: methods and technology used. *Technologies and Trends in the Halal Industry*, Routledge, 2023, pp. 123–138.

[5] T. Manoj, K. Makkithaya, V. Narendra, A blockchain-based credentials for food traceability in agricultural supply chain, in: 2023 IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing, VLSI, Electrical Circuits and Robotics (DISCOVER), IEEE, 2023, pp. 19–24.

[6] M.P. Caro, M.S. Ali, M. Vecchio, R. Giuffreda, Blockchain-based traceability in Agri-Food supply chain management: a practical implementation, in: 2018 IoT Vertical and Topical Summit on Agriculture-Tuscany (IOT Tuscany), IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–4.

[7] T. Sivaram, Recent developments and challenges using blockchain techniques for peer-to-peer energy trading: a review, *Results Eng.* (2024) 103666.

[8] P. Selvaprabhu, Utilizing ethereum blockchain and smart contracts to transform cord blood procurement in health care supply chains, *Results Eng.* 26 (2025) 104867.

[9] M.H. Ali, L. Chung, A. Kumar, S. Zailani, K.H. Tan, A sustainable blockchain framework for the halal food supply chain: lessons from Malaysia, *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Change* 170 (2021) 120870.

[10] M. Casati, C. Soregaroli, G.L. Frizzi, S. Stranieri, Impacts of blockchain technology in agrifood: exploring the interplay between transactions and firms' strategic resources, *Supply Chain Manag.: Int. J.* 29 (7) (2024) 51–70.

[11] A. Srivastava, K. Dashora, Application of blockchain technology for agrifood supply chain management: a systematic literature review on benefits and challenges, *Benchmark: Int. J.* 29 (10) (2022) 3426–3442.

[12] M. Aggarwal, P. Rani, P. Rani, P. Sharma, Revolutionizing agri-food supply chain management with blockchain-based traceability and navigation integration, *Clust. Comput.* (2024) 1–24.

[13] A. Sharma, T. Bhatia, R.K. Singh, A. Sharma, Developing the framework of blockchain-enabled agri-food supply chain, *Bus. Process Manag. J.* 30 (1) (2024) 291–316.

[14] K. Duan, H. Onyeaka, G. Pang, Leveraging blockchain to tackle food fraud: innovations and obstacles, *J. Agric. Food Res.* (2024) 101429.

[15] H.A. Al-Shami, S. Abdullah, Halal food industry certification and operation challenges and manufacturing execution system opportunities. A review study from Malaysia, *Mater. Today: Proc.* 80 (2023) 3607–3614.

[16] J. Jalaluddin, A. Azhar, G. Muzainah, M. Aseri, M.F. Al Amruzi, Proliferation of halal regulation and enforcement in Indonesia and Malaysia, *J. Hum. Rights Cult. Leg. Syst.* 4 (1) (2024) 194–208.

[17] R. Hendayani, Y. Fernando, Adoption of blockchain technology to improve halal supply chain performance and competitiveness, *J. Islam. Mark.* 14 (9) (2023) 2343–2360.

[18] M.H. Ali, L. Chung, K.H. Tan, Z.M. Makhbul, Y. Zhan, M.-L. Tseng, Investigating blockchain technology adoption intention model in halal food small and medium enterprises: moderating role of supply chain integration, *Int. J. Logist. Res. Appl.* (2023) 1–25.

[19] K.Y. Chan, J. Abdullah, A.S. Khan, A framework for traceable and transparent supply chain management for agri-food sector in malaysia using blockchain technology, *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl.* 10 (11) (2019).

[20] A. Tan, D. Gligor, A. Ngah, Applying blockchain for halal food traceability, *Int. J. Logist. Res. Appl.* 25 (6) (2022) 947–964.

[21] S.P. Tan, et al., A review on post-COVID-19 impacts and opportunities of agri-food supply chain in Malaysia, *PeerJ* 11 (2023) e15228.

[22] M.O. Elfarnawani and M. Kartiwi, "Perspectives of stakeholders on the application of blockchain technology in halal supply chain in Malaysia," 2024.

[23] A. Alamsyah, N. Hakim, R. Hendayani, Blockchain-based traceability system to support the Indonesian halal supply chain ecosystem, *Economies* 10 (6) (2022) 134.

[24] I. Vanany, J.M. Soon-Sinclair, N.A. Rahkmawati, Assessment of halal blockchain in the Indonesian food industry, *J. Islam. Mark.* 15 (6) (2024) 1498–1518.

[25] J. Kalajdjieski, M. Raikwar, N. Arsov, G. Velinov, D. Gligoroski, Databases fit for blockchain technology: a complete overview, *Blockchain: Res. Appl.* 4 (1) (2023) 100116.

- [26] H. Patel, B. Shrimali, AgriOnBlock: secured data harvesting for agriculture sector using blockchain technology, *ICT Express* 9 (2) (2023) 150–159.
- [27] A. Shahid, A. Almogren, N. Javaid, F.A. Al-Zahrani, M. Zuair, M. Alam, Blockchain-based agri-food supply chain: a complete solution, *IEEE Access* 8 (2020) 69230–69243.
- [28] G. Zhao, et al., Blockchain technology in agri-food value chain management: a synthesis of applications, challenges and future research directions, *Comput. Ind.* 109 (2019) 83–99.
- [29] J.E. Olesen et al., "AgriFoodTure: roadmap for sustainable transformation of the Danish Agri-Food system," 2021.
- [30] S. Doshi, S. Jangir, P. Gohil, Role of blockchain technology in enhancing supplychain traceability, transparency and efficiency, *J. Exp. Agric. Int.* 46 (5) (2024) 636–653.
- [31] I.M.M. Sheriff, D.J. Aravindhar, Integrated blockchain-based agri-food traceability and deep learning for profit-optimized supply chain management in agri-food supply chains, in: 2024 Fourth International Conference on Advances in Electrical, Computing, Communication and Sustainable Technologies (ICAECT), IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [32] S. Babu, H. Devarajan, Agro-food supply chain traceability using blockchain and IPFS, *Int. J. Adv. Comput. Sci. Appl.* 14 (1) (2023).
- [33] R.W. Ahmad, K.-M. Ko, A. Rashid, J.J. Rodrigues, Blockchain for food industry: opportunities, requirements, case studies, and research challenges, *IEEE Access* (2024).
- [34] E. Daraghmi, S. Jayousi, Y. Daraghmi, R. Daraghmi, H. Fouchal, Smart contracts for managing the agricultural supply chain: a practical case study, *IEEE Access*, 12 (2024) 125462–125479.
- [35] M.P. Kramer, L. Bitsch, J. Hanf, Blockchain and its impacts on agri-food supply chain network management, *Sustainability* 13 (4) (2021) 2168.
- [36] A. Tharatipyakul, S. Pongnumkul, User interface of blockchain-based agri-food traceability applications: a review, *IEEE Access*. 9 (2021) 82909–82929.
- [37] Z. Raza, I.U. Haq, M. Muneeb, Agri-4-all: a framework for blockchain based agricultural food supply chains in the era of fourth industrial revolution, *IEEE Access* 11 (2023) 29851–29867.
- [38] N.A. Nik Ibrahim, A.H. Ahmad Tarmizi, K.R. Selvaduray, A. Kuntom, Sustainability and traceability in the Malaysian oil palm industry. *Recent Advances in Edible Fats and Oils Technology: Processing, Health Implications, Economic and Environmental Impact*, Springer, 2022, pp. 425–461.
- [39] M. Jaradat, M. Al-Manasreh, A. Juaidi, F. Manzano-Agugliaro, Renewable process heat from solar thermal: poultry slaughterhouse processes, *Results Eng.* 21 (2024) 101968.
- [40] P. Pelé, J. Schulze, S. Piramuthu, W. Zhou, IoT and blockchain based framework for logistics in food supply chains, *Inf. Syst. Front.* 25 (5) (2023) 1743–1756.
- [41] I. Hasan and M.M. Habib, "Enhancing transparency in agri-food supply chain by securing IoT-generated data with blockchain," 2024.
- [42] U. Agarwal, V. Rishiwal, M. Shiblee, M. Yadav, S. Tanwar, Blockchain-based intelligent tracing of food grain crops from production to delivery, *Peer-to-Peer Netw. Appl.* 17 (6) (2024) 3722–3749.
- [43] A. Pashaei, M.E. Akbari, M.Z. Lighvan, A. Charmin, Early Intrusion Detection System using honeypot for industrial control networks, *Results Eng.* 16 (2022) 100576.
- [44] H. Ding, et al., Blockchain standards, *Blockchains: Empower. Technol. Ind. Appl.* (2023) 315–348.
- [45] A.J. Menezes, P.C. Van Oorschot, S.A. Vanstone, *Handbook of Applied Cryptography*, CRC press, 2018.
- [46] V. Venukumar, V. Pathari, A survey of applications of threshold cryptography—proposed and practiced, *Inf. Secur. J.: Glob. Perspect.* 25 (4-6) (2016) 180–190.
- [47] S. Jing, X. Zheng, Z. Chen, Review and investigation of merkle tree's technical principles and related application fields, in: 2021 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Big Data and Algorithms (CAIBDA), IEEE, 2021, pp. 86–90.
- [48] A.R. Singh, R.S. Kumar, M. Bajaj, B.H. Kumar, V. Blazek, A blockchain consortium-based framework to enhance interoperability, standardization, and secure demand response management in smart grid applications, *Results Eng.* (2025) 106056.
- [49] V. Harish, R. Sridevi, and K.S. Rao, "Efficient consensus algorithm for split-join blockchain framework: a comparative analysis of PoW, PoS, and PoA".
- [50] W. Adhiwibowo, W. Widayat, W.A. Syafei, Design of dual blockchain-based with point of authority for halal traceability system application on fresh meat-based supply chain, *Results Eng.* (2025) 105133.
- [51] N. Atalan-Helicke, Halal certification in the United States and the expansion of Halal markets. *Religious Economies in Secular Context: Halal Markets, Practices and Landscapes*, Springer, 2023, pp. 21–55.
- [52] IFANCA, "Islamic Food and Nutrition Council of America (IFANCA)," ed, 2012.
- [53] M.S. Christo, A unified elliptic curve cryptographic algorithm for secure communication and homomorphic encryption: A multi-parameter (Built-in CIA) approach, *Results Eng.* (2025) 105354.
- [54] S. Punitha, K. Preetha, A novel integration of web 3.0 with hybrid chaotic-hippo-optimized blockchain framework for healthcare 4.0, *Results Eng.* 24 (2024) 103528.
- [55] A.A. Muhamed, N. Salim, M.N. Ab Rahman, F.M. Hamzah, M.H. Ali, Effects of supply chain orientation on firm performance: insights from a Malaysian case study of halal-certified small and medium-sized enterprises, *J. Small Bus. Entrep.* 35 (6) (2023) 927–943.
- [56] S.D. Rajendran, N.H. Kamarulzaman, A.A. Rahman, The mediating role of halal supply chain integrity in enhancing performance for halal herbal-based food SMEs, *J. Islam. Mark.* 15 (12) (2024) 3621–3648.
- [57] B. Harsanto, J.I. Farras, E.A. Firmansyah, M. Pradana, A. Apriyadi, Digital technology 4.0 on halal supply chain: a systematic review, *Logistics* 8 (1) (2024) 21.
- [58] L. Zare, M.B. Ali, E. Rauch, Industry 5.0 and SMEs future work competency fields: a literature review, in: *International Symposium on Industrial Engineering and Automation*, Springer, 2024, pp. 200–208.
- [59] S. Kumar, K.C. Ramaswamy, S.R. Mathiyalagan, J. Giri, M. Kanan, An efficient battery management system for electric vehicles using IoT & blockchain, *Results Eng.* (2025) 106284.
- [60] A. Morchid, R. Jebabra, H. Qjidaa, R. El Alami, M.O. Jamil, Agri-tech innovations for sustainability: a fire detection system based on MQTT broker and IoT to improve environmental risk management, *Results Eng.* 24 (2024) 103683.
- [61] K.M. Miller, K. Lukic, B. Skiera, The impact of the general data protection regulation (GDPR) on online tracking, *Int. J. Res. Mark.* (2025).
- [62] A. Ali, V. Snásel, J. Platoš, Health-FedNet: a privacy-preserving federated learning framework for scalable and secure healthcare analytics, *Results Eng.* (2025) 106484.